

0/26

Opinions and experiences of Persons with Parkinson's on artificial intelligence (AI) and self-tracking

Fields marked with * are mandatory. ✕

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Anonymous mode ✕
The anonymous option has been activated. As a result, your contribution to this survey will be anonymous as the system will not save any personal data such as your IP address.

Views

Standard

Language

English

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Opinions and experiences of Persons with Parkinson's on artificial intelligence (AI) and self-tracking

The purpose of this survey is to better understand the opinions and experiences of persons with Parkinson's on artificial intelligence (AI) and self-tracking. The results will be used in an ongoing project called AI-PROGNOSIS. For more information about the project, see <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu> (<https://www.ai-prognosis.eu>)

Please read through this information before ticking the 'yes' box below if you wish to participate.

Data collected via this survey will be stored according to regulation of the responsible institute, Uppsala University, Sweden, and used for the purpose of informing the AI-PROGNOSIS project and broader research contributions (publications). Uppsala University is attending personal data according to EU regulation (GDPR 2016/679, art. 6). Data protection officer could be reached at Uppsala University, +46 18 471 20 70, dataskyddsbud@uu.se. This project was submitted for ethical review and was deemed exempt from formal approval by The Swedish Ethical Review Authority Dnr 2024-05505-01. This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no. 101080581. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of The European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Participation in the survey is voluntary, and your response is anonymous.

* By checking the box below, I certify that I have read the above information and agree to participate in this survey.

I agree to participate in a survey for the AI-PROGNOSIS project

* Have you been diagnosed with Parkinson's disease? If not, you are unfortunately ineligible to participate at this time.

Yes, I have been diagnosed with Parkinson's

Background information

* 1. Please indicate your country of residence

- | | | | |
|---|--|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Afghanistan | <input type="radio"/> Dominican Republic | <input type="radio"/> Lithuania | <input type="radio"/> San Marino |
| <input type="radio"/> Albania | <input type="radio"/> Ecuador | <input type="radio"/> Luxembourg | <input type="radio"/> Sao Tome and Principe |
| <input type="radio"/> Algeria | <input type="radio"/> Egypt | <input type="radio"/> Madagascar | <input type="radio"/> Saudi Arabia |
| <input type="radio"/> Andorra | <input type="radio"/> El Salvador | <input type="radio"/> Malawi | <input type="radio"/> Senegal |
| <input type="radio"/> Angola | <input type="radio"/> Equatorial Guinea | <input type="radio"/> Malaysia | <input type="radio"/> Serbia |
| <input type="radio"/> Antigua and Barbuda | <input type="radio"/> Eritrea | <input type="radio"/> Maldives | <input type="radio"/> Seychelles |
| <input type="radio"/> Argentina | <input type="radio"/> Estonia | <input type="radio"/> Mali | <input type="radio"/> Sierra Leone |
| <input type="radio"/> Armenia | <input type="radio"/> Eswatini | <input type="radio"/> Malta | <input type="radio"/> Singapore |
| <input type="radio"/> Australia | <input type="radio"/> Ethiopia | <input type="radio"/> Marshall Islands | <input type="radio"/> Slovakia |
| <input type="radio"/> Austria | <input type="radio"/> Fiji | <input type="radio"/> Mauritania | <input type="radio"/> Slovenia |
| <input type="radio"/> Azerbaijan | <input type="radio"/> Finland | <input type="radio"/> Mauritius | <input type="radio"/> Solomon Islands |
| <input type="radio"/> Bahamas | <input type="radio"/> France | <input type="radio"/> Mexico | <input type="radio"/> Somalia |
| <input type="radio"/> Bahrain | <input type="radio"/> Gabon | <input type="radio"/> Micronesia | <input type="radio"/> South Africa |
| <input type="radio"/> Bangladesh | <input type="radio"/> Gambia | <input type="radio"/> Monaco | <input type="radio"/> South Korea |
| <input type="radio"/> Barbados | <input type="radio"/> Georgia | <input type="radio"/> Mongolia | <input type="radio"/> South Sudan |
| <input type="radio"/> Belarus | <input type="radio"/> Germany | <input type="radio"/> Montenegro | <input type="radio"/> Spain |
| <input type="radio"/> Belgium | <input type="radio"/> Ghana | <input type="radio"/> Morocco | <input type="radio"/> Sri Lanka |
| <input type="radio"/> Belize | <input type="radio"/> Greece | <input type="radio"/> Mozambique | <input type="radio"/> Sudan |
| <input type="radio"/> Benin | <input type="radio"/> Grenada | <input type="radio"/> Myanmar | <input type="radio"/> Suriname |
| <input type="radio"/> Bhutan | <input type="radio"/> Guatemala | <input type="radio"/> Namibia | <input type="radio"/> Sweden |

- 0/26
- Bolivia
 - Bosnia and Herzegovina
 - Botswana
 - Brazil
 - Brunei Darussalam
 - Bulgaria
 - Burkina Faso
 - Burundi
 - Cabo Verde
 - Cambodia
 - Cameroon
 - Canada
 - Central African Republic
 - Chad
 - Chile
 - China
 - Colombia
 - Comoros
 - Congo
 - Costa Rica
 - Côte D'Ivoire
 - Croatia
 - Cuba
 - Cyprus
 - Czechia
 - Democratic Republic of the Congo
 - Denmark
 - Djibouti
 - Dominica
 - Guinea Bissau
 - Guinea
 - Guyana
 - Haiti
 - Honduras
 - Hungary
 - Iceland
 - India
 - Indonesia
 - Iran
 - Iraq
 - Ireland
 - Israel
 - Italy
 - Jamaica
 - Japan
 - Jordan
 - Kazakhstan
 - Kenya
 - Kiribati
 - Kuwait
 - Kyrgyzstan
 - Laos
 - Latvia
 - Lebanon
 - Lesotho
 - Liberia
 - Libya
 - Liechtenstein
 - Nauru
 - Nepal
 - Netherlands
 - New Zealand
 - Nicaragua
 - Niger
 - Nigeria
 - North Korea
 - North Macedonia
 - Norway
 - Oman
 - Pakistan
 - Palau
 - Panama
 - Papua New Guinea
 - Paraguay
 - Peru
 - Philippines
 - Poland
 - Portugal
 - Qatar
 - Republic of Moldova
 - Romania
 - Russian Federation
 - Rwanda
 - Saint Kitts and Nevis
 - Saint Lucia
 - Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
 - Samoa

- 164 Hello **Jamie LUCKHAUS** (logout) | Help | Language
- Switzerland
 - Syrian Arab Republic
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 - Trinidad and Tobago
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 - United Arab Emirates
 - United Kingdom
 - United States of America
 - Uruguay
 - Uzbekistan
 - Vanuatu
 - Venezuela
 - Viet Nam
 - Yemen
 - Zambia
 - Zimbabwe

* 2. Please indicate your age

Maximum 1 selection(s)

- 20 41 63 84
- 21 43 64 85
- 22 44 65 86
- 23 45 66 87
- 24 46 67 88
- 25 47 68 89
- 26 48 69 90
- 27 49 70 91
- 28 50 71 92
- 29 51 72 93
- 30 52 73 94
- 31 53 74 95
- 32 54 75 96
- 33 55 76 97
- 34 56 77 98
- 35 57 78 99
- 36 58 79 100
- 37 59 80 Other
- 38 60 81
- 39 61 82
- 40 62 83

* 3. Please indicate your gender

- Woman Other
- Man Prefer not to specify
- Non-binary

* 4. Highest completed education level

- No formal education Higher education: Bachelor's
- Primary school Higher education: Master's
- Secondary/High school Higher education: PhD or similar
- Vocational education

* 5. How comfortable are you in using digital technology (such as a smartphone, computer, or smartwatch)?

- 1- Not at all
- 2- A little
- 3- Decently
- 4- Very comfortable

* 6. How many years have passed since your Parkinson's diagnosis?

5 character(s) maximum

Use of technologies for Parkinson's disease

Self-tracking is the practice of individuals monitoring and recording information about their own behaviors, symptoms, or bodily functions—such as physical activity, diet, sleep, or mood—often using digital tools or apps, to gain insights and manage health or well-being. Self-tracking can be used in different chronic conditions, for example Parkinson.

* 1. Do you currently **self-track** any signs/symptoms **related to Parkinson's Disease**?

- I do currently
- I do not currently, but I intend to
- I do not currently, and I do not intend to
- I do not currently, but I have in the past

AI, or **artificial intelligence**, is a technology where computers learn to "think" and solve problems in ways similar to humans. There are numerous forms of AI, such as generative AI, a type of AI that can create new content and ideas, including conversations, stories, images, videos, and music.

* 2. Have you used any of these generative AI tools **for any purpose**?

- ChatGPT
- Google's Gemini
- Microsoft's Bing AI
- Claude
- Copilot
- Other generative AI chatbots
- No, I have not used generative AI
- I don't know

Prognosis

In this section, we ask you to think about PD prognosis in general. Here, **prognosis** refers to how your disease is likely to develop including motor and non-motor symptoms, and over what timeline.

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to assist in Parkinson's prognosis and medication response through developing predictive AI models. **Predictive AI** involves AI systems that use data and patterns to predict what might happen in the future. In medicine, this might mean predicting how Parkinson's disease will progress, helping patients and healthcare providers prepare better treatments or manage symptoms more effectively. It's like having a smart companion who can help anticipate what might happen next, enabling proactive care. Although there is currently no way of accurately predicting a PD prognosis, there are research projects aiming at changing this, and for that reason we wish to know your opinion.

1. Prognosis - motor condition

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
*I would be interested to know my PD prognosis in terms of future overall motor condition .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

2. Prognosis - disease milestones

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
*I would be interested to know my PD prognosis in terms of development of future disease milestones . Possible milestones may include onset of cognitive dysfunction, hallucinations, freezing of gait, or dysphagia (swallowing difficulties).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

3. Actionable insights

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
*I would be interested to know which factors may affect my PD prognosis.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I would only be interested in feedback which I can act upon .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

AI system for PD: smartphone app, smartwatch, AI

In this section, we will use the term "**system**" to refer to such an AI-based PD monitoring and prediction system (AI models, smartphone app, smartwatch) for self-tracking and monitoring your PD with the help of your attending doctor.

* 1. What features would you find most helpful in an AI-based tool for managing Parkinson's Disease? (Select all that apply)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Early diagnosis (thinking back to before your PD diagnosis) | <input type="checkbox"/> Tracking symptoms |
| <input type="checkbox"/> PD risk assessment (thinking back to before your PD diagnosis) | <input type="checkbox"/> Providing educational resources |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Personalized treatment recommendations | <input type="checkbox"/> Enhancing patient and caregiver engagement |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Predicting disease progression | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

2. Privacy and trust

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
*Educational content about how the AI prediction works and uses my data would increase my trust in using the system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I would like to choose what data from the system to share with my healthcare provider.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 3. I would like an AI-based system to track the following... (Check all that apply)

- Resting tremor (via a smartwatch)
- Slowness of finger and hand movement (via a smartwatch and smartphone)
- Dyskinesias (via a smartwatch)
- Daytime sleepiness (via a smartwatch)
- Cognitive function (via interactive tests on a smartphone)
- Balance, posture and gait (via interactive camera-based tests on a smartphone)
- I would not like an AI-based system to track (these) symptoms

4. Symptom tracking

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
*To assess my Parkinson's impact over time, I would like the system to enable me to self-select a few (2-3) activities or tasks (such as brushing my teeth or dressing) that I can track my performance of on a regular basis.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*Seeing graphs of my symptoms over time—like day by day or week by week—and alongside my daily activities would help me understand my data better.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
*I'd be willing to enter information myself—like answering questions or doing short tests—not just rely on the system to collect data automatically.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 5. How much time would you be willing to spend on digital tests that check your thinking or movement abilities?

- 30 min/day
- 30 min/week
- 30 min/month
- 30 min/each 6 months
- I do not want to track my symptoms on a smartphone app
- Other

6. Medication tracking

0/26	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* I would like to have the option to enter my medication schedule and receive reminders through the app.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Motivators

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* Gamification (streak count, rewards) of self-tracking, e.g. for wearing the smartwatch or inputting data as much as possible, would help motivate me to consistently use the system for monitoring my PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7a. Are there any other gamification elements you would prefer? (Please specify)

* 8. If the AI system detected changes in your health condition (e.g. worsening symptoms or changes in prognosis), what would your desired course of action be?

- App notifies you only
- App notifies your healthcare professional but not you
- App notifies your healthcare professional who notifies you at your next doctor's visit
- App notifies you and your healthcare professional
- Other

Please add any other comments about the use of AI tools in relation to Parkinson's or on the survey itself

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